

As on 15-01-2017, the following data entry protocol is recommended for recording accuracy flag of data piece in metadata table.

As academic and public good data on underutilised crops is limited, the search for the information required has to include a wide range of sources. This includes various online sources such as blogs and articles as well as advocacy documents which is of variable quality and reliability. As information is gathered and recorded from various sources, it is necessary to categorise these data sources. This is an important step as the source of the data directly affects the data validity and thus affects the quality of outputs derived. In order to facilitate transparency and make the best use of the data that is available, CFF has adopted a protocol which will be used to rate the quality of the data entered in the database (*Table 1*). The data accuracy flag system provides an indication of data quality.

Table 1: Underutilised crops data source accuracy colour categories and description

Colour categories	Description
Reliable	CFF research data CFF curated and validated data
Caution	Journals Government departments Agriculture-related companies/websites Farmer's blog's Newspaper Agriculture books
Unreliable / No Data / Filler	Non-Agricultural-related Websites Non-Agriculture-related Blogs

Green

These are data derived from CFF research programmes. Collected data which are validated by CFF experts. All collected data are flagged as 'Amber' or 'Red' prior to CFF expert curation and validation.

Amber

This category includes a wide range of data which are from Journals (Review/Research Articles), Ministry of Agriculture, Department of Agriculture, Agricultural-related Organization, Agriculture-related Companies, Agricultural-related Websites/Blogs, Universities Websites/Sources, Farmers' blogs, Newspaper Websites, Published Agricultural/Botanical Books. Examples of sources are given in *Table 2*.

Table 2: Examples of amber category data sources

Sources	Examples
Journals (Review/Research Articles)	Journal of Botany
Ministry of Agriculture	MOA Malaysia
Department of Agriculture	USDA, DOA Malaysia, DOA States
Agricultural-related Organization	FAO, CABI, GBIF
Agriculture-related Companies	http://www.stevia.com/index.aspx
Agricultural-related Databases/Websites/Blogs	-EOL -Ecocrop -Agroforestry (AFT) -Agrifarming.in: http://agrifarming.in/tag/vigna-mungo-cultivation -Anim Agro Technology: http://animhosnan.blogspot.my/2015/08/herba-dokong-anak-part-1.html [in Malay Language]
Universities Websites/Sources	TamilNadu Agricultural University: http://agritech.tnau.ac.in/agriculture/agri_index.html

Farmers' blogs (The farmer handling the cultivation of the searched crop himself publishing the data)	http://mybaha76.blogspot.my/2011/09/bab-21-buat-duit-dengan-tanam-serai.html [in Malay Language]
Newspaper Websites	http://www.sinarharian.com.my/rencana/koko-berpotensi-bernilai-tinggi-1.2204 [in Malay Language]
Published Agricultural/Botanical Books	https://books.google.com.my/books?id=i7YgZ-LAHPgC&printsec=frontcover#v=onepage&q&f=false
Unpublished Materials- Manuscript/Thesis regarding crops	http://psasir.upm.edu.my/6768/1/IB_2005_10(1-24).pdf

Red

Data from Non-Agricultural-related Websites and Non-Agriculture-related Blogs (*Table 3*).

Table 3: Examples of red category data sources

Sources	Examples
Non-Agricultural-related Websites	http://homeguides.sfgate.com/grow-vigna-mungo-30182.html
Non-Agriculture-related Blogs	e.g. blogger writing on something about their discovery/experience on certain crop during their trip for holiday vacation